

Variation in isolates of *Sclerotium oryzae*, the rice stem rot pathogen

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Sclerotium oryzae (conidial state, *Helminthosporium sigmoideum* Cav., and ascigerous state, *Magnaporthe salvinii*

Krause and Webster) is the causal agent of stem rot of rice. It causes significant yield losses in India and neighboring countries. The pathogen varies in morphological and cultural behavior even among the isolates collected from the same geographic area. We studied the variability of five isolates collected from Bangladesh (SO-B), India (SO-I), Nepal (SO-N), Pakistan (SO-P), and Sri

Lanka (SO-S) to document cultural, sclerotial, and other characters.

The isolates varied in colony and sclerotial characters. Appressoria varied mainly in size and number of lobes appressorium⁻¹. Sclerotia viability was highest in isolate SO-N at 30°C and at room temperature but maximum viability in isolate SO-I occurred at the surface of the soil (see table). ■

Comparison of different *S. oryzae* isolates.

Character	SO-B	SO-I	SO-N	SO-P	SO-S
Average colony diameter in mm (5th day)	64.33	63.00	74.66	56.66	62.33
Color of colony	White	Cottony white	White	White	White
Time taken for sclerotial initiation (h)	144	120	120	96	124
Color of sclerotia	Shiny black	Black	Black	Brownish black	Black
Sclerotial pattern	Scattered round	Scattered round	Embedded in mycelium	Scattered round	Scattered round
Size of sclerotia (µm)	296.5	247.3	255.3	214.9	224.9
Color of appressorium	Light brown	Brown	Brown	Brown	Brown
Size of appressorium					
Length (mm)	11-27	12-29	14-30 z	14-26	12-27
Width (mm)	9-27	9-25	8-26	11-24	9-22
Number of lobes appressorium ⁻¹	10	9	9	11	10
Viability of sclerotia at					
30°C (mo)	16	17	19	16	17
room temperature (mo)	19	20	24	17	18
soil surface (mo)	9	11	10	8	9

Integrated pest management—insects

Susceptibility to insecticides of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* in the lower Yangtze Valley

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Adult brown planthopper (BPH), more than 50 females of each population, have been collected from ricefields of Anqing (Anhui Province) and Yangzhou (Jiangsu Province) and multiplied with rice in the laboratory at 25°C, 16 h photoperiod since 1989. Assays were conducted using female adults of F₂-F₃ within 5 d after emergence by the

topical treatment method. Technical grade insecticides were dissolved in analytical grade acetone and five or more diluted concentrations were prepared. For each concentration, 50 macropterous females were treated with 0.05 µL of solution applied by microsyringe on the thoracic dorsum. Monitoring was done 48 h after treatment. Dose-mortality regressions were estimated by probit analysis. LD₅₀s were considered to be indicative of resistance and their differences among years were tested by t test. The formula used was

$$t = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{\sqrt{s_{m_1}^2 - s_{m_2}^2}}$$

where $m_1 = \log LD_{50}$ and $s_{m_1}^2$ or $s_{m_2}^2$ is the variance of m_1 or m_2 , respectively. If t is >1.96 or <-1.96 , there is significant difference between m_1 and m_2 .

The results are shown in the table. Although LD₅₀s fluctuated among years, resistance ratios varied little when compared with those in 1995. The reduction of the dosage of conventional insecticides applied to BPH in recent years has resulted from the wide application of buprofezin and of rice varieties resistant to BPH. ■

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